

Avifaunal diversity of Pakke Tiger Reserve in the Eastern Himalaya hotspot of Arunachal Pradesh, India

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Abstract

Fifty-two species of birds belonging to 29 families were recorded in Pakke Tiger Reserve, Arunachal Pradesh, India. The highest number of species belonged to the family Muscicapidae with eight, Accipitridae, Bucerotidae, Columbidae, Phasianidae, and Pycnonotidae each with three species, while Ardeidae, Campephagidae, Falconidae, Megalaimidae, Phylloscopidae and Scolopacidae with two species each. The remaining seventeen families viz., Alcedinidae, Charadriidae, Chloropseidae, Coraciidae, Corvidae, Dicruridae, Eurylaimidae, Irenidae, Laniidae, Locustellidae, Motacillidae, Oriolidae, Phalacrocoracidae, Picidae, Strigidae, Sturnidae, and Vangidae with one species were recorded. IUCN (International Union for Conservation of Nature) conservation status of two species (*Rhyticeros undulatus* and *Buceros bicornis*) under VU (Vulnerable), two species (*Vanellus duvaucelii* and *Treron phayrei*) under NT (Near Threatened), while the remaining are categorized under LC (Least Concern).

Keywords: Arunachal Pradesh, Birds, Pakke tiger reserve, IUCN

Introduction

Birds are excellent indicators of ecosystem health, fascinating and widely-studied taxa. They are among the most diverse group of vertebrates in tropical forests and because of their high local diversity and abundance, they are involved in key ecological processes such as arthropod control, pollination, and seed dispersal (Sekercioglu, 2006). The North-eastern state of Arunachal Pradesh is part of two global biodiversity hotspots (the Eastern Himalaya and Indo-Burmese biodiversity hotspots) (Mittermeier *et al.*, 2004) as well as two 'Endemic Bird Areas' (the Eastern Himalaya

and the Assam Plains) (Stattersfield *et al.*, 1998). Pakke Tiger Reserve (PTR) (26°54'–27°16' N and 92°36'–93°09'E) with a total area of 862km² is located in the foothills of Eastern Himalaya biodiversity hotspot in the East Kameng District of Western Arunachal Pradesh at the junction of the Palearctic and Indo-Malayan zoogeographic realms. PTR is surrounded by a confluence of rivers *viz.*, the Pakke River flowing East, Kameng River in the west and Papu River towards the northern margin. Other rivers include Nameri, Khari, East Kameng and Upper Dikroi with their tributaries. The area is characterized by lowland semi-evergreen, evergreen forests and Eastern Himalayan broadleaf forests and by undulating hilly terrain with altitudes ranging from 200 m to about 2000 m above sea level (Kumar and Solanki, 2008). This Protected area was declared as the 'Pakhui Wildlife Sanctuary' in 1977 and due to its large tiger population composition, it was declared 'Pakke Tiger Reserve' in 2002 (Chaudhry *et al.*, 2016).

The PTR is also surrounded by major protected areas and forests; the Southern part lies adjacent to Nameri Tiger Reserve in Assam, the north with Tenga reserve forest, west by the Doimara Reserve Forest and east by Papum Reserve Forest. Topographically characterised by rugged mountains with a peak altitude of 2,000 meters above mean sea level, it has different forest types including Assam Valley tropical semi-evergreen forests, Sub Himalayan light alluvial semi-evergreen forests, Eastern Hollock Forests, Upper Assam Valley tropical evergreen forests, Tropical riverine forests and Secondary moist bamboo tracts (Datta *et al.*, 1998). PTR has major frugivorous and granivorous birds and flower peckers facilitating ornithochory (Sethi and Howe, 2009; TCP, 2014). PTR is an Important Bird Area (IBA) (Islam and Rahmani, 2004) and studies on its avian diversity have been carried out earlier indicating 282 species as the highest count (Datta *et al.*, 1998; Birand and Panwar, 2004; Kumar 2014; Kumar, 2020).

Material and methods

Study area: The area covered during the present survey is the southeastern margin extending from Langka Village to Bhalukpung camp of the PTR and the different campsites around the survey area are indicated in Table 1 and Figure 1.

Table 1. Location of campsites in the study area during the survey

Sl. No.	Name of Location	GPS
1	Pakke Jungle Camp, Seijusa	26°59'05.9"N 93°01'55.5"E
2	West Bank Forest Camp	26°56'20.6"N 92°58'43.2"E
3	Golosa Camp	26°58'32.2"N 93°02'33.4"E

4	Mobusa Camp	26°58'58.2"N 93°03'31.5"E
5	Dibru	27°01'02.6"N 93°02'29.0"E
6	Langka	27°02'29.1"N 93°01'55.4"E
7	Pakke Nature Information Centre	26°56'15.6"N 92°58'45.3"E
8	Upper Dikroi/Tarzen camp	27°02'03.9"N 92°40'04.5"E
9	Khari	26°58'48.8"N 92°55'15.5"E
10	Anti-Poaching Camp east Nameri	27°02'38.8"N 92°46'06.7"E
11	Forest Camp near Balukpong	27°01'06.8"N 92°38'35.1"E

Figure 1. Pakke tiger reserve in Western Arunachal Pradesh (Source: Google Maps)

Species were recorded through direct visual observations and were classified using photographic methods for verification. The field surveys birds were done using a convenience sampling approach by foot between 01 to 10 December 2015. The observations were done during 5:00 -12 hrs and 19:00-21:00 hrs every day. Birds were photographed opportunistically using a Canon Nikon-D7100 camera and identified using field guide (Grimmett *et al.* 2011).

Results

Fifty-two species of birds belonging to 29 families were recorded during the present survey with the highest number of species (n=8) belonging to Muscicapidae. Muscicapidae is represented by 72 species a feature common to Northeast India (Datta *et al.* 1998). Accipitridae, Bucerotidae, Columbidae, Phasianidae, and Pycnonotidae each with three species, while Ardeidae,

Campephagidae, Falconidae, Megalaimidae, Phylloscopidae and Scolopacidae with two species each. The remaining seventeen families viz., Alcedinidae, Charadriidae, Chloropseidae, Coraciidae, Corvidae, Dicruridae, Eurylaimidae, Irenidae, Laniidae, Locustellidae, Motacillidae, Oriolidae, Phalacrocoracidae, Picidae, Strigidae, Sturnidae, and Vangidae with one species were recorded. However, the lesser number of species is attributed to opportunistic count and all the birds recorded have already been reported in earlier studies (Supplementary figures and table).

The Ashy-headed Green Pigeon *Treron phayrei* (Blyth, 1862) and River Lapwing, *Vanellus duvaucelii* (Lesson, 1826) are listed as ‘Near threatened’ as per the IUCN status. Two species viz., Wreathed Hornbill, *Rhyticeros undulatus* (Shaw, 1811), Great Hornbill, *Buceros bicornis* (Linnaeus, 1758) are listed as ‘Vulnerable’, while the remaining are categorized under LC (Least Concern). Five species viz., *Motacilla alba* Linnaeus, 1758, *Phoenicurus leucocephalus* (Vigors, 1831), *Phoenicurus fuliginosus* (Vigors, 1831), *Vanellus duvaucelii* (Lesson, 1826), *Phalacrocorax carbo* (Linnaeus, 1758) were recorded near aquatic ecosystem. Both the sexes of *Tephrodornis virgatus* and *Pericrocotus flammeus* (Forster, 1781) were also recorded. One species, *Oriolus traillii* (Vigors, 1832) was reported as in juvenile stage. *Treron phayrei* (Blyth, 1862), *Megalurus palustris* Horsfield, 1821 *Psilopogon zeylanicus* (Gmelin, 1788) *Phoenicurus hodgsoni* (Moore, 1854) *Saxicola leucurus* (Blyth, 1847) *Ficedula ruficauda* (Swainson, 1838) were infrequently sighted in the reserve area.

Discussion

The survey provided information on the avifauna observed opportunistically during a faunal survey on Ephemeropterans over a short duration. However, it’s worthy of information considering not many follow-up studies have been undertaken after that. Also, considering the fact that North Eastern India with the highest avian diversity in India has many threatened species (Maheswaran and Alam, 2017). Interesting records have been obtained during the study, India has 17 out of the total 51 species of pheasants, and Arunachal Pradesh has 11 species, 80% of India’s total pheasants (Selvan *et al.*, 2013). They are Himalayan or Impeyan Monal *Lophophorus impejanus*, Sclater’s Monal *L. sclateri*, Blyth’s *Tragopan blythii*, Satyr *Tragopan satyra*, Temminck’s *Tragopan temminckii*, Blood Pheasant *Ithaginis cruentus*, Mrs. Hume’s Pheasant *Syrnaticus humiae*, Tibetan Eared Pheasant *Crossoptilon harmani*, Grey Peacock Pheasant *Polyplectron bicalcaratum*, Kaleej Pheasant *Lophura leucomelanos* and Red Jungle fowl *Gallus gallus*. The latter three were recorded during the present survey. Existence of birds is determined by their habitat owing to the availability of food and shelter and most pheasant species are considered ‘indicator species’ due their sensitivity to habitat changes. The grey peacock pheasant, *P.*

bicalcaratum recorded during the survey was found entangled in the trap set by hunters, it was safely retrieved and released into wild. Three (Great Hornbill, Oriental Pied Hornbill and Wreathed Hornbill) of the four hornbill species (Oriental pied hornbill, wreathed hornbill, the rufous-necked hornbill and the great hornbill) occurring in the reserve were recorded in this survey. The great hornbill is the state bird of Arunachal Pradesh, a reduction in hunting hornbills and protection due to increased awareness among the local Nishi community has conservation implications in the region (Datta, 1998, Datta *et al.* 2008). PTR has a special attribute as IBA, particularly good for raptors since seventeen including rarities such as the Pallas's Fish-Eagle are recorded hereof the 66 species reported from the Indian subcontinent (BirdLife International, 2023). Three have been observed during this study *viz.*, *Spilornis cheela* (Latham, 1790), *Circus cyaneus* (Linnaeus, 1766) and *Milvus migrans* (Boddaert, 1783). Although the present survey was undertaken in December 2015, very few surveys/online portals enumerating avifaunal diversity have been undertaken in PTR except 221 species of bird by Kumar, 2020 and 290 species reported in eBird (2021). The latter is enabled with a reporting system based on checklists provided by birders and is regularly updated.

Conclusion

The present data would contribute to the body of avifaunal diversity records of PTR. Conservation initiatives concerning protected areas with flagship species like Tiger in the present case is strongly influenced by involving local communities. Regular diversity records would serve as crucial assessments to conservation initiatives undertaken in a protected area like PTR present in the Eastern Himalayas, one of the four biodiversity hotspots in India.

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Appendix

Supp. table 1. List of avifauna recorded during the study in PTR

Sl. No.	Scientific Name	Common Name	Family	IUCN Status	
	<i>Spilornis cheela</i> (Latham, 1790)	Crested Serpent-Eagle	Accipitridae	LC	
	<i>Circus cyaneus</i> (Linnaeus, 1766)	Hen Harrier			
	<i>Milvus migrans</i> (Boddaert, 1783)	Black Kite			
	<i>Halcyon smyrnensis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	White-Throated Kingfisher	Alcedinidae	LC	
	<i>Bubulcus ibis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Cattle Egret	Ardeidae	LC	
	<i>Egretta garzetta</i> (Linnaeus, 1766)	Little Egret			
	<i>Anthracoceros albirostris</i> (Shaw & Nodder, 1807)	Oriental Pied Hornbill	Bucerotidae	LC	
	<i>Rhyticeros undulatus</i> (Shaw, 1811)	Wreathed Hornbill			VU
	<i>Buceros bicornis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Great Hornbill			VU
	a.) <i>Pericrocotus flammeus</i> (Forster, 1781) b.) <i>Pericrocotus flammeus</i> (Forster, 1781)	Scarlet Minivet	Campephagidae	LC	
	<i>Coracina macei</i> (Lesson, 1831)	Large Cuckoo Shrike			LC
	<i>Vanellus duvaucelii</i> (Lesson, 1826)	River Lapwing	Charadriidae	NT	
	<i>Chloropsis aurifrons</i> (Temminck, 1829)	Golden-Fronted Leaf Bird	Chloropseidae	LC	
	<i>Chalcophaps indica</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Common Emerald Dove	Columbidae	LC	
	<i>Spilopelia chinensis</i> (Scopoli, 1786)	Eastern Spotted Dove			
	<i>Treron phayrei</i> (Blyth, 1862)	Ashy-headed Green Pigeon			NT
	<i>Coracias benghalensis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Indian Roller	Coraciidae	LC	
	<i>Cissa chinensis</i> (Boddaert, 1783)	Common Green Magpie	Corvidae	LC	
	<i>Dicrurus bracteatus</i> (Gould, 1842)	Spangled Drongo	Dicruridae	LC	
	<i>Serilophus lunatus</i> (Gould, 1834)	Silver-Breasted Broadbill	Eurylaimidae	LC	

	<i>Microhierax melanoleucos</i> (Blyth, 1843)	Pied Falconet	Falconidae	LC
	<i>Falco tinnunculus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Common Kestrel		LC
	<i>Irena puella</i> (Latham, 1790)	Asian Fairy-Bluebird	Irenidae	LC
	<i>Lanius schach</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Long-Tailed Shrike	Laniidae	LC
	<i>Megalurus palustris</i> (Horsfield, 1821)	Striated Grass Bird	Locustellidae	LC
	<i>Psilopogon australis</i> (Horsfield, 1821)	Blue-Eared Barbet	Megalaimidae	LC
	<i>Psilopogon zeylanicus</i> (Gmelin, 1788)	Brown-Headed Barbet		LC
	<i>Motacilla alba</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	White Wagtail	Motacillidae	LC
	<i>Phoenicurus fuliginosus</i> (Vigors, 1831)	Plumbeous Water-redstart	Muscicapidae	LC
	<i>Phoenicurus hodgsoni</i> (Moore, 1854)	Hodgson's Redstart		LC
	<i>Copsychus saularis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Oriental Magpie-Robin		LC
	<i>Ficedula westermanni</i> (Sharpe, 1888)	Little Pied Flycatcher		LC
	<i>Saxicola leucurus</i> (Blyth, 1847)	White-Tailed Stonechat		LC
	<i>Saxicola torquatus</i> (Linnaeus, 1766)	Common Stonechat		LC
	<i>Phoenicurus leucocephalus</i> (Vigors, 1831)	White-Capped Redstart		LC
	<i>Ficedula ruficauda</i> (Swainson, 1838)	Rusty-Tailed Flycatcher		LC
	<i>Oriolus traillii</i> (Vigors, 1832)	Maroon Oriole (juvenile)	Oriolidae	LC
	<i>Phalacrocorax carbo</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Great Cormorant	Phalacrocoracidae	LC
	<i>Lophura leucomelanos</i> (Latham, 1790)	Kalij Pheasant	Phasianidae	LC
	<i>Gallus gallus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Red Jungle Fowl		LC
	<i>Polyplectron bicalcaratum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Grey Peacock-Pheasant		LC
	<i>Phylloscopus intermedius</i> (La Touche, 1871)	White-Spectacled Warbler	Phylloscopidae	LC
	<i>Phylloscopus xanthoschistos</i> (Gray, 1845)	Grey-Hooded Warbler		LC
	<i>Picus chlorolophus</i> (Vieillot, 1818)	Lesser Yellow Nape	Picidae	LC
	<i>Pycnonotus cafer</i> (Linnaeus, 1766)	Red-Vented Bulbul	Pycnonotidae	LC
	<i>Alophoixus flaveolus</i> (Gould, 1836)	White-Throated Bulbul		LC
	<i>Pycnonotus melanicterus</i> (Gmelin, 1789)	Black-Capped Bulbul		LC
	<i>Tringa ochropus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Green Sandpiper	Scolopacidae	LC
	<i>Actitis hypoleucos</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Common Sandpiper		LC
	<i>Glaucidium cuculoides</i> (Vigors, 1831)	Asian Barred Owlet	Strigidae	LC
	<i>Sturnia malabarica</i> (Gmelin, 1789)	Chestnut-tailed starling	Sturnidae	LC
	a.) <i>Tephrodornis virgatus</i> (Temminck, 1820) Male	Large Wood-Shrike	Vangidae	LC
	b.) <i>Tephrodornis virgatus</i> (Temminck, 1820) Female			

Note: LC=Least Concern, VU=Vulnerable, NT=Near Threatened

1. *Spilornis cheela* (Latham, 1790) 2. *Circus cyaneus* (Linnaeus, 1758) 3. *Milvus migrans* (Boddaert, 1766) 4. *Halcyon smyrnensis* (Linnaeus, 1758)

5. *Bubulcus ibis* (Linnaeus, 1758)

6. *Egretta garzetta* (Linnaeus, 1758)

7. *Anthracoceros albirostris* (Linnaeus, 1758)

8. *Rhyticeros undulatus* (Shufeldt, 1811)

9. *Buceros bicornis* Linnaeus, 1758

10. a) *Pericrocotus flammiceps* (Forster, 1781) Female

10. b) *Pericrocotus flammiceps* (Forster, 1781) Male

11. *Coracina macei* (Lesser, 1831)

12. *Vanellus duvaucelii* (Lesser, 1826)

13. *Chloropsis aurifrons* (Temminck, 1829)

14. *Chalcophaps indica* (Linnaeus, 1758)

15. *Spilopelia chinensis* (Scopoli, 1786)

16. *Treron phayrei* (Blyth, 1842)

17. *Coracias benghalensis* (Linnaeus, 1758)

18. *Cissa chinensis* (Boddaert, 1783)

19. *Dicrurus bracteatus* (Günther, 1842)

20. *Serilophus lunatus* (Goulet, 1834)

21. *Microhierax melanoletus* (Blyth, 1843)

22. *Falco tinnunculus* Linnaeus 1758

23. a) *Irena puella* (Latham, 1790) (Female)

23.b) *Irena puella* (Latham, 1790) Juvenile Male

24. *Lanius schach* (Linnaeus, 1758)

25. *Megalurus palustris* (Horsfield, 1821)

26. *Psilopogon australis* (Horsfield, 1821)

27. *Psilopogon zeylanicus* (Gmelin, 1788)

28. *Motacilla alba* (Linnaeus, 1758)

29. *Phoenicurus fuliginosus* (Vigors, 1831)

30. *Phoenicurus hodgsonii* (Moore, 1854)

31. *Copsychus saularis* (Linnaeus, 1758)

32. *Ficedula westermani* (Sharpe, 1888)

33. *Saxicola leucurus* (Blyth, 1843)

34. a) *Saxicola torquatus* (Linnaeus, 1766)

34. *Saxicola torquatus* – ferrugineus (Linnaeus, 1766)

35. *Phoenicurus leucocephalus* (Vigors, 1831)

36. *Ficedula ruficauda* (Swainson, 1838)

37. *Oriolus traillii* (Vigors, 1831) Juvenile

38. *Phalacrocorax carbo* (Linnaeus, 1758)

39. *Lophura leucomelanotos* (Latham, 1790)

40. *Gallus gallus* (Linnaeus, 1758)

41. *Polyplectron bicalcaratum* (Linnaeus, 1758)

42. *Phylloscopus intermedius* (Touche, 1898)

43. *Phylloscopus xanthoscolarius* (Gray, 1846)

44. *Phylloscopus xanthoscolarius* (Gray, 1846)

45. *Pycnonotus cafer* (Linnaeus, 1766)

46. *Alophoixus flaveolus* (Günther, 1836)

47. *Pycnonotus melanictes* (Gmelin, 1789)

48. *Tringa ochropus* (Linnaeus, 1758)

49. *Actitis hypoleucos* (Linnaeus, 1758)

50. *Glaucidium cuculoides* (Vig
1831)

51. *Sturnia malabarica* (Gm
1789)

52. a) *Tephrodornis virgatus*
(Temminck, 1824) Female

52. b) *Tephrodornis virgatu*
(Temminck, 1824) Male

Sup. figures 1-52. Birds observed during the present survey